

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A Note on Full k -Ideals in Ternary Semirings

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Abstract

Objectives: k – ideals plays a vital role in ternary semirings. Ternary algebraic systems is a generalization of algebraic structures and it is the most natural way for the further development, deeper understanding of their properties.

Methods: We have imposed Integral Multiple Property (IMP) and some other different constrains on a ternary semiring. **Findings:** In this study, we have described more results on the full k -ideal in the ternary semirings. Finally, we provide the characterization of full k -ideal in ternary semirings and studied their related properties. **Applications:** The structures of ideals in ternary semirings are widely applicable to computer sciences, dynamical and logical systems, cryptography, graph theory and artificial intelligence.

Keywords: Ternary Semiring; Ideal; k - Ideal; Full k - Ideal; Inverse

1 Introduction

The first formal definition of semiring was introduced in the year 1934 by Vandiver⁽¹⁾. Several researches have characterized the many type of ideals on the algebraic structures such as: In 1958, Iséki considered and proved some theorems on quasi-ideals in semirings. However the developments of the theory in semirings have been taking place since 1950. A semiring is basic structure in Mathematics. The semiring theory and semigroup theory influenced on the developments of the semiring theory and its ordering. Nagi Reddy U, Rajani K, and Shobhalatha G have studied the fuzzy bi-ideals in ternary semigroups⁽²⁾. Ternary rings are introduced with their structures⁽³⁾. Some properties of ternary semirings are derived with the quasi ideals and Bi ideals⁽⁴⁾. S^* semirings and A^* semirings, which are studied with the some special structures⁽⁵⁾. Certain type of ring congruences on an additive inversive semirings with the help of full k -ideals is studied⁽⁶⁾. Sen and Adhikari gave some characterizations of maximal k -ideals of semiring.

Our main purpose of this paper is to introduce the notions of k - ideals and full k - ideals in ternary semirings and study the set of all full k -ideals of an additively inverse ternary semiring in which addition is commutative forms a complete lattice which is

also modular.

2 Preliminaries

Definition 2.1: A Ternary semiring is a nonempty set S together with the binary operation addition and ternary operation multiplication denoted by $+$, \cdot respectively, satisfying the following conditions:

1. $(S, +)$ is a commutative semigroup.
2. (S, \cdot) is ternary semigroup.
3. Distributive laws holds, i.e., $a \cdot b(c+d) = a \cdot b \cdot c + a \cdot b \cdot d$ $a(b+c)d = a \cdot b \cdot d + a \cdot c \cdot d$ and $(a+b) \cdot c \cdot d = a \cdot c \cdot d + b \cdot c \cdot d$

Definition 2.2: An element a of a ternary semiring S is said to be additive idempotent element provided $a+a=a$.

Note: The set of all additive idempotent elements in a ternary semiring S is denoted by $E^+(S)$.

That is $E^+(S) = \{a \in S/a + a = a\}$.

Definition 2.3: A ternary semiring S is called E -inverse, if for every $a \in S$, there exists $x \in S$ such that $a + x \in E^+(S)$.

Note: Let S be a ternary semi ring, then $E^+(S)$ is an ideal of S .

Definition 2.4: A subset I of a ternary semiring S is called a left (resp. a right, lateral) ideal of S if

1. $a + b \in I$ for all $a, b \in I$
2. for any $a \in I$, and $b, c \in S, bca \in I$ (resp. $abc \in I, bac \in I$)

A subset I is called an ideal if I is left, lateral and right ideal.

Note:

1. If A, B are any two ideals of a ternary semiring S , then $A \cap B$ is an ideal.
2. Let A, B be two ideals of a ternary semiring S , then the sum of A, B denoted by $A + B$ is an ideal of S where $A + B = \{x = a + b \mid a \in A, b \in B\}$

Definition 2.5: An ideal I of a ternary semiring S is called full if $E^+(S) \subseteq I$

Example: In any ternary ring R , the set $E^+(R) = \{0\}$, and so every ideal of R is a full ideal.

Definition 2.6. An ideal I of a ternary semiring S is called k -ideal or subtractive if for any two elements $a \in I$ and $x \in S$ such that $a + x \in I$, then $x \in I$.

Example. In any ternary ring R , every ideal I is k -ideal, since for any $a \in I, x \in R$ such that $a + x \in I$ then $a + x + (-a) \in I$ so $x \in I$

Definition 2.7. A k -ideal I of a ternary semiring S is called full k -ideal if the set of all additive idempotents of S , $E^+(S)$ is contained in I .

Example 1: In any ternary ring R every ideal I is a full k -ideal. Since 0 is the only additive idempotent element in R which belongs to any ideal I of R . So I is full k -ideal.

Example 2: In a distributive lattice L with more than two elements, a proper ideal I is k -ideal but not full k -ideal. Let $a \in I, x \in L$ such that $a \vee x \in I$, then $x \leq a \vee x$. But I is an ideal so $x = x \wedge (a \vee x) \in I$. Hence I is k -ideal. Moreover, the set of all additive idempotents of L is L itself, since $a \vee a = a$ for all $a \in L$. So I is not full k -ideal.

Example 3: In $Z \times Z^+ = \{(a, b) : a, b \text{ are integers and } b > 0\}$ we define $(a, b) + (c, d) = (a + c, lcm(b, d))$ and $(a, b) \cdot (c, d) \cdot (e, f) = (a \cdot c \cdot e, gcd(b, d, f))$, then $Z \times Z^+$ is an additive inversive ternary semiring.

Solution: Let $(a, b), (c, d), (e, f) \in Z \times Z^+$

Additive commutative:

$$(a, b) + (c, d) = (a + c, lcm(b, d)) = (c + a, lcm(b, d)) = (c, a) + (a, b)$$

Additive associative:

$$\begin{aligned} ((a, b) + (c, d)) + (e, f) &= ((a + c, lcm(b, d)) + (e, f)) \\ &= (((a + c) + e, lcm(lcm(b, d), f))) \\ &= ((a + (c + e), lcm(b, lcm(d, f)))) \\ &= (a, b) + ((c + e), lcm(d, f)) \\ &= (a, b) + ((c, d) + (e, f)). \end{aligned}$$

Multiplicative associative: Similarly as additive associative Distributive:

$$\begin{aligned} (a, b) \cdot (c, d)((e, f)) + (g, h) &= (a, b) \cdot (c, d)(e + g, \text{lcm}(f, h)) \\ &= (a \cdot c(e + g), \text{gcd}(b, d, \text{lcm}(f, h))) \\ &= (a \cdot c \cdot e + a \cdot c \cdot g, \text{lcm}(\text{gcd}(b, d, f), \text{gcd}(b, d, h))) \\ &= (a \cdot c \cdot e, \text{gcd}(b, d, f)) + (a \cdot c \cdot e, \text{gcd}(b, d, h)) \\ &= ((a, b) \cdot (c, d)(e, f)) + ((a, b) \cdot (c, d)(g, h)) \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $((e, f)) + (g, h)(a, b) \cdot (c, d) = ((e, f)(a, b) \cdot (c, d) + (g, h)(a, b) \cdot (c, d))$

Additive inverse: For any $(a, b) \in Z \times Z^+$ there exists a unique $(-a, b) \in Z \times Z^+$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} (a, b) + (-a, b) + (a, b) &= (a + -a + a, \text{lcm}(b, b, b)) = (a, b), \\ (-a, b) + (a, b) + (-a, b) &= (-a + a + -a, \text{lcm}(b, b, b)) = (-a, b) \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, the set $A = \{(a, b) \in Z \times Z^+ - a = 0, b \in Z^+\}$ is full k-ideal of $Z \in Z^+$.

Since $E^+(Z \times Z^+) = \{0\} \times Z^+ \subseteq A$ and for any $(0, b) \in A, (c, d) \in Z \times Z^+$ such that $(0, b) + (c, d) = (c, \text{lcm}(b, d)) \in A$, then $c = 0$, so $(c, d) \in A$.

Definition 2.8: Let A be an ideal of an additive inversive ternary semiring S. We define the k-closure of A, denoted by \bar{A} by:

$$\bar{A} = \{a \in S \cdot a + x \in A \text{ for some } x \in A\}$$

Definition 2.9: A lattice L is called a modular lattice simply modular, if for $a, b, c \in L, a \leq b \implies a \wedge c = b \wedge c \implies a \vee c = b \vee c$ implies $a = b$.

3 Main Results

Theorem 3.1. Let A and B be two full k-ideal of a ternary semiring S. then $A \cap B$ is full k-ideal.

Proof. Let A and B be two full k-ideal of S, then $A \cap B$ is an k ideal which is full as $E^+(S) \subseteq A$ and $E^+(S) \subseteq B$

Let $x \in S$ such that $a + x \in A \cap B$ for some $a \in A \cap B$. Then $a + x \in A, a \in A$ and $a + x \in B, a \in B$ which implies that $x \in A$ and $x \in B$.

Hence, $x \in A \cap B$

Therefore, $A \cap B$ is full k-ideal.

Theorem 3.2. Every k-ideal of ternary semiring S is an inversive sub semiring of S.

Proof. Clearly that every ideal of S is sub semiring of S. Let $a \in I$, then $a \in S$, so there exist $a' \in S$ such that $a = a + a' + a = a + (a' + a) \in I$.

But I is a k-ideal and $a \in I$, so $a' + a \in I$. Again I is a k-ideal and $a \in I$, so $a' \in I$.

Hence I is an inversive sub semiring of S.

Theorem 3.3. Let A be an ideal of ternary semiring S. Then A is a k-ideal of S. Moreover $A \subseteq \bar{A}$.

Proof. Let $a, b \in \bar{A}$, then $a + x, b + y \in A$ for some $x, y \in A$.

Now $(a + b) + (x + y) = (a + x) + (b + y) \in A$.

But $x + y \in A$, so $a + b \in \bar{A}$. Next let $p, r \in S$, then $pra + prx = pr(a + x) \in A$.

But $prx \in A$, so, $pra \in \bar{A}$. Similarly, $apr \in A$.

Since \bar{A} is an ideal of S.

To show that \bar{A} is k-ideal.

Let $c, c + d \in \bar{A}$, then there exist x and y in A such that $c + x \in A$ and $c + d + y \in A$.

Now $d + (c + x + y) = (c + d + y) + x \in A$ and $c + x + y \in A$.

Hence $d \in \bar{A}$ and so \bar{A} is a k-ideal of S.

Finally, since $a + a \in A$ for all $a \in A$, it follows that $A \subseteq \bar{A}$.

Corollary 3.1 Let A be an ideal of ternary semiring S. Then $\bar{A} = A$ if and only if \bar{A} is a k-ideal.

Proof. Suppose $\bar{A} = A$, then by theorem 3.3 \bar{A} is k-ideal, and so A is k-ideal.

Conversely, assume that A is a k-ideal. Again by theorem 3.3 $A \subseteq \bar{A}$.

On the other hand, let $a \in \bar{A}$ then $a + x \in A$ for some $x \in A$. But A is a k-ideal and $x \in A$, implies $a \in A$, so $\bar{A} \subseteq A$. Therefore $A = \bar{A}$.

Corollary 3.2: Let A and B be two ideals of a ternary semiring S such that $A \subseteq B$, Then $\bar{A} \subseteq \bar{B}$.

Proof. Let A and B be two ideals of S such that $A \subseteq B$, let $a \in \bar{A}$, then $a + x \in A$ for some $x \in A$, but $A \subseteq B$, so $a + x \in B$ for some $x \in B$.

Hence $a \in \bar{B}$, Therefore $\bar{A} \subseteq \bar{B}$.

Corollary 3.3: Let A be an ideal of ternary semiring S . Then \bar{A} is the smallest k -ideal containing A .

Proof. Let B be a k -ideal of S such that $A \subseteq B$, let $x \in \bar{A}$. Then $x + a_1 = a_2$ for some $a_1, a_2 \in A$.

Since $A \subseteq B$ and B is a k -ideal, then $x \in B$.

This implies that $\bar{A} \subseteq B$.

Therefore \bar{A} is the smallest k -ideal containing A .

Theorem 3.4: Let A and B be two full k -ideals of ternary semiring S . then $\overline{A+B}$ is a full k -ideal of S such that $A \subseteq \overline{A+B}$ and $B \subseteq \overline{A+B}$.

Proof. Let A and B be two full k -ideals of ternary semiring S . Then $A+B$ is an ideal of S .

Then by theorem 3.3 $\overline{A+B}$ is a k -ideal and $A+B \subseteq \overline{A+B}$.

Now $E^+(S) \subseteq A$ and $E^+(S) \subseteq B$. So for any $e \in E^+(S)$, $e = e + e$.

Hence $E^+(S) \subseteq A+B \subseteq \overline{A+B}$. Which implies that $\overline{A+B}$ is a full k -ideal.

Finally let $a \in A$, Then $a = a + a' + a = a + (a' + a) \in A+B$ as $a' + a \in E^+(S) \subseteq B$

Hence $A \subseteq \overline{A+B}$ and similarly $B \subseteq \overline{A+B}$.

Theorem 3.5: The set of all full k -ideals of ternary semi ring S . denoted by $I(S)$, is a complete lattice which is also modular.

Proof. Firstly we note that $I(S)$ is a partially ordered set with respect to usual set inclusion. Let $A, B \in I(S)$. Then by Theorem 3.1 $A \cap B \in I(S)$, and by Theorem 3.4, $\overline{A+B} \in I(S)$.

Define $A \wedge B = A \cap B$ and $A \vee B = \overline{A+B}$.

It is clearly that $A \cap B = \inf\{A, B\}$, let $C \in I(S)$ such that $A, B \subseteq C$.

Then $A+B \subseteq C$ and $\overline{A+B} \subseteq C$. But $C = \bar{C}$.

Which implies that $\overline{A+B} \subseteq C$.

Hence $\overline{A+B} = \sup\{A, B\}$. Thus we find that $I(S)$ is a lattice.

If S be a ternary semiring, then $E^+(S)$ is an ideal of S .

Thus $E^+(S)$ is an ideal of S , which contained in every ideal in $I(S)$.

Hence $\overline{E^+(S)}$ is the smallest full k -ideal in $I(S)$, and also $S \in I(S)$.

Consequently $I(S)$ is a complete lattice.

Finally to show that $I(S)$ is modular.

Suppose that $A, B, C \in I(S)$ such that $A \wedge B = A \wedge C$ and $A \vee B = A \vee C$ and $B \subseteq C$.

Let $x \in C$. we have $C \subseteq \overline{A+C} = A \vee C$, so $x \in A \vee C = \overline{A+B}$.

Hence there exists $a+b \in A+B$ such that $x+a+b = a_1+b_1$ for some $a_1 \in A, b_1 \in B$.

Then $x+a+a'+b = a_1+b_1+a'$.

But $x \in C, a+a' \in E^+(S) \subseteq C$

Since C is full ideal and $b \in B \subseteq C$, then $a_1+b_1+a' \in C$. But $b_1 \in B \subseteq C$, which is k -ideal.

So $a_1+a' \in C$, also $a_1+a' \in A$ which implies that $a_1+a' \in C \cap A = A \cap B$.

Hence $a_1+a' \in B$.

So from (1), We find that $x+a+a'+b = a_1+a'+b \in B$. But $(a+a')+b \in B$, which is a k -ideal.

Which implies that $x \in B$.

Hence $B=C$.

Therefore $I(S)$ is a modular lattice.

4 Conclusions

We considered the notion of k -ideals and fully k ideals in ternary semirings and studied their properties and relations between them.

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